

USE OF MEDIA TECHNOLOGY TO REVITALIZE THE MYTH OF AMBU HAWUK FOR LANGUAGE TEACHING MATERIAL IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

Media technology at this time is a bridge that can connect efforts to revitalize myths as part of oral literature with the implementation of language learning in the multiliteracy era as a challenge in the 21st century. Revitalizing myths can be done by transforming them into the performing arts of musical poetry developed through technological media. The practice of art-based research in this study is a method that can pave the way in that direction. This is evidenced by the concretization of the revitalization product of the Ambu Hawuk myth into the performing arts of musical poetry as a multimedia performing art. In the end, the revitalization product of oral literature can be used in language learning to answer two challenges simultaneously: transmitting cultural values and carrying out language learning using aesthetic technology.

Keywords: Media Technology, Revitalize, Ambu Hawuk Myth, Language Teaching Material, 21st Century

INTRODUCTION

Efforts to revitalize oral literature (fairy tales, legends, and myths) can be aligned with efforts to create language learning that intersects with technology. This is based on the birth of multiliteracy, a marker for literacy development. It then gives rise to the notion that language learning will be more meaningful if it intersects with context, culture, and technology (Abidin, 2015, p. 7). About context and culture, content regarding oral literature, whether in the form of fairy tales, legends, or myths, can be used as learning material about revitalization issues within the scope of oral literature research.

Revitalizing myths is something that needs to be done to prevent the extinction of oral literature which is usually followed by the extinction of oral traditions which causes the loss of traditional society to the loss of ethnic wisdom as cultural heritage (Rusyana, 2006, p. 1; Amir, 2013, p. 6; Sibarani, 2012, pp. 1, 12, 13; Godoy, et al., 1998; McDade, et al., 2007; Reyes-Garcia, et al., 2005, 2007; Ross, 2002). On this basis, the alignment of efforts to revitalize oral literature with efforts to present language teaching materials that contain social and cultural values is a real challenge today.

The development of multimedia performing arts can be used as the estuary of a process that defines harmony between efforts to revitalize oral literature and efforts to create multiliterate language learning. Its concreteness lies in the effort to present teaching materials in the form of multimodal texts that can be used in language learning.

Based on the facts above, the position of multimodal text has an important role in problems in learning related to the use of verbal language to present teaching materials in class (Kress, 2001, p. 1; Moreno & Mayer, 2007, p. 310). This is why the issue of multimodality is in great demand among academics, which is marked by the rise of writings in the form of books, journals, and others that discuss multimodal and its research (Jewitt, 2016, p. 1). Multiliteracy is the skill of using a variety of ways to express and understand ideas and information using conventional and innovative text forms, symbols, and multimedia (Abidin, 2015, p. 51). In this context, language functions as a carrier, collector, and developer of knowledge. Every scientific discipline is taught to students not only about their body of knowledge but also about how to see, think, and communicate. Furthermore, whatever knowledge students learn, language is used as the main tool for thinking (Burke, 2013, p. 1). About the 2013 curriculum, learning Indonesian is directed at developing knowledge of texts which then leads to the ability to compose texts, to be communicated orally and in writing.

Few studies seek to revitalize oral literature by concretizing it in the form of multimedia performing arts as new multimodal texts. Research conducted by Darma (2011) and Riswandi, et al (2021) on the myth of Ambu Hawuk and Galunggung oral literature has only attempted to transform oral literature into drama scripts. Research conducted by Setiartin (2018) tried to create a learning model centered on making animated comics based on the Ambu Hawuk myth. The novelty of the research conducted by the author lies in the creation of multimedia performing arts based on the Ambu Hawuk myth as a concrete effort to revitalize oral literature and create multiliterate learning through a transformation process by utilizing art-based research practices.

METHOD

Art-based research in this study begins with qualitative research (Ethnography) which functions to explore oral data about the myth of Ambu Hawuk. Data exploration was carried out by collecting and analyzing oral data to study Galunggung culture and society. The data obtained through this research are more unstructured or in other words, data that have not been formulated in coded form as a set of categories that still receive opportunities for certain analysis (Koentjaraningrat, 2002, p. 329; Fathoni, 2005, p. 98; Spradley, 2007, p. 4; Herdiansyah, 2010, p. 75). The ultimate goal of the research is to find out the content, function, and value of the Ambu Hawuk myth.

Then the research continued to art-based research which aims to make multimedia performing arts a multimodal text in language teaching. The form of multimedia performing arts in this study is poetry and musical performances in a multimedia frame. The selection of performing arts of poetry musicalization as a form of research product is adjusted to the revitalization objectives that are relevant to efforts to create language teaching materials. This is in line with Leavy's explanation (2017, p. 222) that the selection of artistic representation media needs to be selected and considered based on its ability to produce and represent the content and convey it aesthetically. Based on the above, for technical purposes, the research design in this study is described as follows.

Figure 1. Research Design

Ethnographic research was carried out in Leuwisari District, Tasikmalaya Regency. This sub-district is located in the Galunggung Region, Tasikmalaya Regency. Sources of research data on Ambu Hawuk oral literature come from Abah Anong (age 90), Ajengan Ali (age 60), and Kang Gun Gun (age 40) as oral literature practitioners in the area. The participant involved in the ethnographic research was Dede Rahmat (age 40s) as an intermediary or liaison between the author and data sources. The research data obtained is oral data on the myth of Ambu Hawuk based on the results of interviews with the main participants. The research data were analyzed using an inductive technique with the stages of (1) collecting, analyzing, reading, and studying the data by tagging keywords and ideas in the data; (2) data classification based on data themes; and (3) interpreting the resulting data.

Art-based research is carried out in collaboration with participants who are artists, including Yana S. Atmawiharja as a poet, Alfin Nurul Azmi as a composer for musicalization of poetry, Septia Pahlawan as a painter, Ai Mellyana Agustin and friends as dancers, and several people others as poetry readers and multimedia editors. The artworks produced by the participants are research data that are composed to form a complete multimedia performance art in the form of poetry and musical performances.

Qualitative research data collection techniques (ethnography) in this study were carried out in a "natural setting". Some of the methods used are participant observation, interviews, and documentation which is commonly known as the triangulation method (Sugiono, 2011, p. 383). Besides that, this research data collection also uses an art process/art-making process. In the process of making art, research data is collected through an artistic process in certain mediums (Greenwood, 2019, p. 8).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Art-Based Research Practice and Myth Revitalization Model

Efforts to preserve oral literature cannot only be done by memorizing stories or rewriting oral texts into books. Oral literature has the potential to be developed through the creation of multimedia improvisational spaces. This is done so that oral literature can come into contact with today's society so that its values and norms can be actualized and transmitted (Sibarani, 2012, p. 2; Amir, 2013, pp. 6 – 7).

The revitalization model in this study is a model that was created and developed to reconstruct myth as part of oral literature into the multimedia form so that it can be in direct contact with the target of transmission and is practically used in language learning. The creation and development of this model are also based on the findings of the Ambu Hawuk myth in the form of incomplete oral speech as is normally the case in narrative prose or other oral literature. To

revitalize the Ambu Hawuk myth, a model is needed that is able to reconstruct the story so that it can be conveyed to the wider community. In this study, the revitalization of the Ambu Hawuk myth is carried out through reconstruction, re-functionalization, representation, reform, reinterpretation, reorientation, and recreation. The concretization of this pattern is carried out through the steps of recognition, documentation, transfer, and dissemination to the public in the form of multimedia performing arts. The form of revitalization in this study is a form of the artificial revitalization of oral literature. It means presenting the myth of Ambu Hawuk in the form of multimedia performance art through planning and engineering processes. In this process, the mythical form of Ambu Hawuk underwent a process of transformation, both expansion, and conversion (Sumiyadi, 2016; Sibarani, 2012; Durachman, 2016).

The process of revitalizing oral literature in the form of myths in this study uses art-based research methods. Arts-based research is a methodological and epistemological approach that combines research with one or more works of art in social research. The position of art is used as a tool to find out and as a means of investigation and proper representation of a social phenomenon. This is due to the notion that the process of art production opens up opportunities to explore the knowledge and meaning of phenomena in depth and interactively (Eisner, 1998; 2002; Jagodzinski & Wallin, 2013; Knowles & Cole, 2008; Parsons & Boydel, 2012; Leavy, 2015, p. ix; Leavy, 2017, p. 191; Leavy, 2020, p. 4; Burnard, et.al., 2018; Greenwood, 2019).

Art-based research emerges from a combination of artistic practices in the arts with scientific or social scientific practices (Gergen & Gergen, 2011; Jones, 2006, 2010, 2013). Research is conducted based on the belief that the arts and humanities can facilitate social scientific goals (Jones, 2010). This statement bridges discussions regarding art-based paradigms and ways of achieving research goals (Leavy, P. 2017, p. 194). Art-based research can be carried out by involving several works of art including literature, music, dance, performances, visual arts, films, and other media. Forms of representation are not limited to short stories, novels, novelettes, creative non-fiction, graphic novels, comics, poetry, parables, collages, paintings, drawings, sculptures, 3-D art, quilts, sewing, scripts, plays, dances, films, songs, and musical scores (Leavy, 2020, p. 4). In this research, the main objective of revitalization is to present myths as part of oral literature in a more practical form for language appreciation and learning. The use and framing of literature, music, painting, and dance in multimedia performing arts is assumed to be a form of mythical representation that the current generation can appreciate as a target for transmitting cultural values.

The revitalization model of oral literature in this study is a model that originates from the process of transforming the myth of Ambu Hawuk into a form of multimedia performance art. The form of performing art that is made in the art of performing musical poetry in which there are several other works of art as a form of representation of the myth of Ambu Hawuk which is assumed to be able to revive the existence of this myth. The myth of Ambu Hawuk in this study underwent two transformation processes, namely spoken text into poetic text and poetic text into multimedia performing arts in the form of performing arts of poetry musicalization. Here's an illustration.

Figure 2. Ambu Hawuk Myth Revitalization Model

Based on the picture above, the revitalization process focuses on the process of transforming the form of spoken text into multimedia art in the form of performing arts of poetry musicalization. Spoken text becomes the initial text (T0) which is studied based on content, function, and cultural values. This study is important because the main objective of revitalizing oral literature is to actualize and transmit values. The perpetrators of this study of oral literary texts are the researchers themselves.

The first transformation process is the transformation of oral literary texts into poetic texts (T1). This transformation is an attempt to sublimate the values contained in the Ambu Hawuk myth into the form of a poetic text as a literary text. In the end, the text of the poem still has the values as in the previous text (T0). The perpetrators in this transfer process are actors of the literary arts after communicating with the author regarding the content and values of the Ambu Hawuk myth.

The process of transformation II is the text of poetry into multimedia art in the form of performing arts of poetry musicalization. In this transformation process, the *mise en scene* method is used to concretize the idea of abstraction by paying attention to the adjustment aspects of the composed poetic text (Pavis, 1991, 2013; Yudiaryani, 2009). The actors in the process of transferring this vehicle are the writer as the director who is assisted by other artists such as dance artists, painting artists, acting artists, poetry reading artists, and poetry musical

composers. With regard to the form of transformation, the myth of Ambu Hawuk in this study underwent language transfer, genre transfer, art transfer, and media transfer (Sumiyadi, 2019, pp. 385-386). The myth of Ambu Hawuk, which was originally in Sundanese, was translated into Indonesian and then translated from oral literature into poetry. Ambu Hawuk's poetry was then converted and converted into musical poetry, painting, dance, and poetry reading, which were then collaborated through a composition process to become multimedia art performing poetry musical performances.

Implementation of the Revitalization Model on the Ambu Hawuk Myth

Based on the results of ethnographic research, the myth of Ambu Hawuk was obtained in the form of speech from several sources. The stories obtained are in the form of incomplete stories and require further interpretation or linking with other stories. This causes the myth of Ambu Hawuk to be reconstructed if it is to be transmitted narratively.

The myth of Ambu Hawuk is a myth that tells of a figure who is actually a holy figure but is also believed to be a "Hawuk" or dark figure due to his supernatural powers of mastering black magic. In a myth that became the basis for writing poetry, Ambu Hawuk 1 represents the content of the myth that breaks all assumptions about the figure of Ambu Hawuk as the figure of "Hawuk." The myth of Ambu Hawuk represented by Ambu Hawuk 1's poetry also reflects how the Sundanese human figure who masters supernatural powers, whose classification of black or white lies in how to use it. Is it for the good or the bad in society? The figure of Ambu Hawuk in the myth is told as a member of the kingdom who does not get his rights as a member of the kingdom. At present, it is said that the figure of Ambu Hawuk often appears in the form of a giant bat perched on a monument in the area around Rumantak Galunggung Tasikmalaya West Java Indonesia.

The story of Ambu Hawuk is folklore that originates from the Galunggung people and developed in the past and is also a characteristic of every nation (Sundanese people) who have Sundanese culture. The story of Ambu Hawuk how the figure of Ambu Hawuk in Galunggung. The story of Ambu Hawuk is a literary expression of the Galunggung people which is transmitted orally and is closely related to the collective memory of the traditional Galunggung society structure when it was still in the form of a kingdom. The contents of the story are anonymous and adventurous and have been disseminated for quite a long time among the Galunggung people.

The implementation of the revitalization model on the myth of Ambu Hawuk starts from the process of transforming the oral text of the myth into a poetic text. In this process, the author collaborates with a poet who is currently completing an anthology of poetry, which has oral literature on Mount Galunggung, Tasikmalaya Regency, West Java, Indonesia as its main theme. The author of the poem is Yana S. Atmawiharja from Garut, West Java, Indonesia, who now lives in the city of Tasikmalaya, West Java, Indonesia. Based on additional oral literature data collected by the author, Yana S. Atmawiharja finally completed her poetry anthology and one of the poems related to the myth of Ambu Hawuk is Ambu Hawuk 1's poem as follows.

Table 1. Ambu Hawuk 1 (in Indonesian)

<p>GALUNGGUNG —Ambu Hawuk I</p> <p>Langit malam lebaran cahaya bulan lebam</p> <p>tidak, tidak ada gerhana atau matahari yang menghendak pagi tapi rekah ekormu barat menyentuh timur</p> <p>Di langit malam lebaran kerling bintang terhalang bukan, bukan awan atau cuaca yang menghendak hujan tapi bentang sayapmu utara menyambang ke selatan</p> <p>: Ambu! Engkau raja tanpa mahkota Hidup terlunta tapi tak sesat, menetap di astana bukan istana sebelum para wali, engkau mengajarkan kebajikan para dewa</p> <p>Ambu! Ketika menemu manusia-manusia linglung di zaman yang limping maka wujudmu adalah hawuk harimau dengan bulu gelap serupa teluh taringmu pedang, algojo yang memenggal siapa saja.</p> <p>Di sebuah tugu, malam lebaran engkau ringkih menjelma perempuan ratusan tahun konde merapal doa, istigfar bagi anak dan cucu.</p> <p>2020</p>

The poem above uses the main title Galunggung as a sign that the poem written has the main object of Galunggung or the wealth of stories found in Galunggung. The subtitle Ambu Hawuk I indicates the specification of the story represented through the poem, about Ambu Hawuk, of

which two episodes are written in this anthology. The poem consists of six stanzas with a different number of lines in each stanza.

Overall the contents of the poem have been able to represent the contents of the myth of Ambu Hawuk as presented in the study section. The poem written by Yana S. Atmawiharja uses many terms that represent the form of Ambu Hawuk which is similar to a giant or a giant bat with the words "ekor (tail)" and "sayap (wings)" and its size is likened to "barat menyentuh timur (west touching east)" and "utara menyambang ke selatan (north facing south)." The composition of the creative ideas carried by Yana S. Atmawiharja in writing Ambu Hawuk I's poetry focuses on the process of contemplation, imagining, and the author's physical journey in the area in Galunggung which is believed to be the place where Ambu Hawuk's presence in myths sparks, explores and matures ideas to be poured on poetry.

The poem above becomes the main work of art which will then be transformed into poetry musical performance art and is produced using multimedia so that it becomes multimedia performing art in the form of poetry musical performances. Furthermore, in the above poem, the tone composition process is carried out in the poem, hereinafter referred to as the musicalization of poetry. The compositional process coincides with the process of representing Ambu Hawuk in the form of painting. Furthermore, the creative process continued with the design of the dance concept as a form of representation of Ambu Hawuk which was adapted to the musical strains of the poem. Furthermore, the creative process continued with designing the concept of poetry reading performances. After everything has been designed, then shooting is carried out on stage or off stage.

Based on the general description above, it can be seen that fragments of works of art that will later be composed into complete multimedia performing arts are the musical arts of poetry, painting, dance, and poetry reading. These artworks will eventually be composed into performance art and framed multimedia using the Adobe Premiere Pro application.

After the text of the poem based on the myth has been written, the process of implementing the model continues with the tone composition of the poem. This creative process was carried out by Alfin Nurul Azmi, a music artist in Tasikmalaya City, West Java, Indonesia. The musicalization of the poem composed by Alfin is played in a minor tone, from the G scale, namely E minor and is written in 4/4 measure with a moderate tempo with a tempo speed of 60 bpm. The musicalization of this poem has a different texture on each beat which tends to go up and down. This is due to Alfin as a composer adjusting the music to the atmosphere or atmosphere of the text of Ambu Hawuk I's poetry. The following is the result of the musical composition of Ambu Hawuk I's poetry in the form of sheet music.

Figure 3. Ambu Hawuk I Poetry Musicalization Score

Voice

AMBU HAWUK

Alfinazmi

$\text{♩} = 60$

la ngit ma lam le ba ran ca ha ya bu lan le bam ti dak ti

dak ada ger ha na a tau ma ta ha ri yang meng hen dak pa gi ta

pi re kah e kor mu ba rat me nyen tuh ti mur di

langit ma lam le ba ran ker ling bin tang ter ha lang bu kan bu

kan awan a tau cuaca yang meng hen dak huan ta pi ben tang sa yap mu

utara menyam bang ke se latan am bu

eng kau ra ja tan pa mah ko ta hi dup ter lun ta ta pi tak se sat

me ne tap di as ta na bu kan is ta na se be

lum pa ra wa li eng kau meng ngajar kan ke

ba ji kan pa ra de wa

Voice

am bu ke tik ka me ne mu ma nu sia ma nu sia linglung di ja

man yang lim pung ma ka wu jud mu a da lah hawuk ha ri

mau de ngan bu lu ge lap se ru pa te luh ta ring mu pe dang

al go jo yang me meng gal si a pa sa ja

di se buah tu gu ma lam le ba ran eng kauring kik men jel ma pe rem puan

ra tu san ta hun kon de me ra pal do a

is tig far ba gi anak dan cu cu

In the musical structure of Ambu Hawuk I above, there is an intro that is filled with prioritizing guitar instruments through distortion effects, as well as melodies from rebab instruments. In the song and chorus, there are vocal elements as the main instrument accompanied by piano instruments and melodies from the Kacapi instrument. In the interlude section, there is a guitar melody using distortion effects and followed by a flute instrument melody accompanied by drum beats. In the end, there is a vocal element accompanied by a piano and a melody from the fiddle instrument.

The use of West Javanese ethnic musical instruments in this musical aims to create the atmosphere conveyed by the poet Ambu Hawuk I in the poem. As explained above, the poem tells about the sacred figure of a Sundanese man. Apart from that, the collaboration of Sundanese musical instruments or West Javanese ethnic musical instruments can provide identity in the musicalization of Ambu Hawuk 1's poetry and can make poetry musical works different from musical poetry in general. Based on this, the musical genre of the musicalization of Ambu Hawuk 1's poetry is World Music. This is due to the involvement of elements of Sundanese ethnic instruments in the composition. The definition of World Music in this composition tends to be a mix or combination of Western and non-Western musical styles compared to world music as the music of nations (Kurniawan, W., 2018, pp. 2 – 3). This combination was carried out by incorporating elements of Sundanese folk music into the Pop Rock music patron as modern music or Western music so that it can be said that the musical composition of Ambu Hawuk's Poetry is a composition of fragments of Sundanese folk music and Pop Rock music (Hybrid) which can be categorized as world music (Kurniawan, W., 2018, p. 3; Erlaman, V., 1990, p. 467).

When Alfin Nurul Azmi composed poetry to musicalize poetry, other creative processes were carried out by Septia Pahlawan. This process is a creative process of transforming the myth of Ambu Hawuk into a painting which will later become one of the tracks of multimedia performing arts. The figure of Ambu Hawuk which forms the basis of Septia Pahlawan's image as a painter is the figure of Ambu Hawuk who is depicted in an abstract way by presenting him as a woman or woman only on a small part of the canvas (approximately 1/6 of the canvas at the top). Paintings of this genre only use descriptions from the chin to the border of the upper lip without other parts of the face. The dominant colors used by painters are black and white. Black is mostly used for the background and white is used as a color to contrast the background so that the figure of Ambu Hawuk is abstractively realized which has black and white properties as depicted in the text of the poem. At the bottom, in an abstract manner, it is also described as a residential area which is a symbol as a member of the people of Mount Galunggung who is always prayed for goodness and good luck in life by Ambu Hawuk, which is also conveyed in the poem by Yana S. Atmawiharja above. The following is the result of Septia Pahlawan's painting.

Figure 4. Painting of Ambu Hawuk by Septia Pahlawan

The next transformation process as a form of implementing the Ambu Hawuk Myth revitalization model is the creative process of dance compositions carried out by Ai Mellyana Agustin. In the early stages of the creation process, it starts with exploring the mythical content of Ambu Hawuk and listening to the musicalization of Ambu Hawuk I's poetry. This stage is an exploratory stage carried out to stimulate the creative power of dance movements (Hadi, 2017, p. 70). At this stage of exploration Ai Mellyana Agustin focuses on the imagination of the figure of Ambu Hawuk as a figure who is actually a holy figure, but is also believed to be a "Hawuk" or dark figure due to his supernatural powers. In the improvisation stage, Ai Mellyana goes through the process freely and spontaneously with an open mind and body that follows the flow of ideas. Furthermore, at the composition stage, Ai Mellyana Agustin began composing, assembling, or arranging movement motifs into a unified whole, or what is called choreography (Hadi, 2017, p. 77). At this stage Ai Mellyana Agustin's creative ideas are centered on aspects of considering the selection of motion to be able to represent or project the figure of Ambu Hawuk aesthetically. Then in the final stage or evaluation stage, Ai Mellyana Agustin used the video recording of the dance she had done to sharpen her creative ideas with the aim of perfecting the dance moves she was doing.

Figure 5. Ambu Hawuk dance by Ai Mellyana Agustin

The next process of transformation is the creative process of an expressive poetry reading performed by Ai Siti Mardiah. In the expressive poetry reading conducted by Ai Siti Mardiah, she used the concept of imagination how to inform the figure of Ambu Hawuk as conveyed by the poet's text through his poetry. There are two characteristics of the figure which is the source of Ai Siti Mardiah's appreciation, the figure of "white" and the figure of "Hawuk" or "black." From these two figures, Ai Siti Mardiah imagined how she would respond to these two figures, if the "white" figure reflected virtue, then she read the text of the poem in a subtle, respectful, and slightly shady way. On the other hand, when it comes to the figure "Hawuk" or "black", Ai Siti Mardiah reads it with fear as if she is facing a figure that will give her bad luck. This is also reflected in the gesture that Ai Siti Mardiah shows through her aesthetically expressive poetry reading as a form of artistic representation of the figure of Ambu Hawuk through the text of a poem written by Yana S. Atmawiharja. The following is a collage of poetry readings by Ai Siti Mardiah.

Figure 6. Expressive Poetry Reading by Ai Siti Mardiah

After all of the art above has been developed by the actors, then the process of taking pictures or videos is carried out. This video was shot on a different stage in line with the predetermined

video composition concept. The first video shot was a dance video taken by Ai Mellyana Agustin (choreographer), Rista Aulia, Imelda Ayu Syaquila Asprilia Dahlan, Rahma Naila Cahya, Silfa Milatul Istiqomah, and Chelsea Putri Kinanti, students who are members of the dance group from the Indonesian Language Education FKIP University Siliwangi Tasikmalaya, West Java, Indonesia. This video was shot above. The video shooting continued with the painting process carried out by Septia Pahlawan. This video was taken not on the stage, but in a building that had not yet been completed. The shooting was carried out at night and assisted by lighting from the lighting system normally used in performances on stage. The next video shot is a poetry reading by Ai Siti Mardiah. The video was taken in a studio with the help of a lighting system that combines red and yellow light. The videos above are taken thoroughly or from start to finish. This is done to provide the necessary stock videos for the video composition process to become a complete multimedia performance art. The video composition process uses the Adobe Premiere Pro application in 2021. In the application, the main basis for video composition is the musical track of the composition of poetry by Alfin Nurul Azmi. This means that the composition of the video fragments in each of the artworks above must be able to represent the content of the musicalization of the poem which will automatically represent the myth of Ambu Hawuk. This indicates that not all of the video fragments taken in each of the artworks above are used in multimedia performance art in the form of poetry and musical performance art.

In the video composition process using the Adobe Premiere Pro 2021 application, the first time is to prepare the musicalization track of Ambu Hawuk 1's poetry. The next step is to combine the components between the poetry musicalization track and the poetry illustration video using. In this composition process, the editor selects video illustration materials that are tailored to the needs of the poetry musical track. Each part of the video must be able to represent the musical track of the poem. After the composition process is complete, then the editor will provide color grading to the video. Similar to drawing on a canvas, the painter will add colors to the image to make it clearer and in accordance with the contents of the image. Likewise, with this color grading process, the editor adjusts the colors in the video to match the feelings in the video. After the color grading process is complete, the next step is that the editor will add a credit title or credit scene as information about the people involved in the process of making the video. Then the video composition that has been edited will go through a rendering process, the rendering process is the process of combining the compositions that have been input into the application to become a complete multimedia performance art.

As a whole, the musical performance of Ambu Hawuk 1's poetry consists of three parts, namely the opening, content, and closing parts. The opening section is preceded by a narration that introduces the viewer into multimedia performing arts. The narrative conveyed is about what and what viewers will watch if they continue to watch multimedia performing arts. Furthermore, in the opening section it is continued with a video of the process of painting and expressive reading of the text of Ambu Hawuk 1's poetry. In the content section, multimedia performance art begins with dance and audio of the musicalization of Ambu Hawuk 1's poetry. In this section, the Ambu Hawuk dance is accompanied by the musicalization of Ambu Hawuk

l's poetry. Furthermore, in the closing section, the names of actors who have contributed to this multimedia performance art are displayed.

Figure 7. Use of Adobe Premiere Pro 2021 in Video Composition

CONCLUSION

Efforts to create multimodal texts for language teaching can be done in various ways and with various contents. One of the contents that can be raised is regional oral literature. Efforts to elevate regional oral literature to be used as multimodal texts are efforts to concretely revitalize oral literature. This can be done through a process of transformation, be it language transfer, genre transfer, art transfer, or media transfer. This is done so that students can have direct contact with revitalization products by utilizing technology, resulting in the strengthening of traditional values and modernization of language teaching. Art-based research is a research approach that can realize the above efforts, collaboratively with artists. This is related to the position of art in ABR, one of which is considered a medium to represent research findings. This form of representation becomes a multimodal text in language teaching that has educational and aesthetic values that can open up wider spaces for interaction.

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